

PROBONO

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY & REPORTING (I)

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001/2018/2001

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Communication Committee
C&D	Dissemination and Communication
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
PC	Project Coordinator
PS	Project Secretariat
SIN	Smart Innovation Norway (Consortium member)
SM	Social Media
TMT	Technical Management Team
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The communication and dissemination strategy and associated materials described in this deliverable lay the foundations of how dissemination and communication activities should unfold in the PROBONO project. They also help ensure that the project can create a significant impact on the broad green building and neighbourhood concept, society, and all stakeholders involved.

This document explains the strategic and tactical actions to accomplish awareness and engagement in the PROBONO project. For this purpose, several tools and activities are defined to establish a long-lasting connection with the project beneficiaries, participants in the project, and other external stakeholders.

Besides tools and activities, the deliverable also explains the internal communication plan for the participation of all partners for a successful dissemination and communication process. Additionally, relevant files, reporting process, contribution guidelines, etc., for dissemination activities of the Communication Committee are presented.

1. Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. D8.1 (Dissemination & Communication Strategy & Reporting) addresses Task 8.1 (Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities) which consists of ST8.1.1 (Dissemination Strategy & Communication Plan), ST8.1.2 (Dissemination & Communication material), and ST8.1.3 (Dissemination & Communication activities). Out of these three subtasks, D8.1 mainly handles the requirements of ST8.1.1 (Dissemination Strategy & Communication Plan). The primary purpose of ST8.1.1 is to establish an agile communication and awareness plan.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 8.1. Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities (M1-M60)	<p>ST8.1.1. Dissemination & Communication Plan.</p> <p>An agile communication and awareness plan will be developed at the beginning of the project, and periodically updated during the project. The output will be a detailed plan for communication and dissemination to achieve the ambitions in this project. The task will incorporate stakeholder mappings & characterisations from WP2, and then use it to have the most appropriate dissemination and communication channels for each stakeholder group and effectively target and tailor messages for each group. The task will build on the preliminary work done in WP2 and will coordinate and manage the communication & dissemination work; additionally, every partner will be responsible for disseminating their results and activities and also those of the project overall. The communication and dissemination activities will be tracked and monitored constantly, thus in every consortium meeting a brief overview will be presented.</p>	Chapter 2-9 and Annexes I-III	Communication and Dissemination Plan is described along with the communication vision, objectives, strategy, activities, tools, and KPIs. "Content Creation Guideline", "Content Creation Schedule", and "Monitoring" files are also included in Annexes I - III.
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D8.1: Dissemination and Communication Strategy & Reporting Establish project communication and dissemination strategy</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

This document lays the foundations of the communication and dissemination activities of the project by establishing the communication and dissemination strategy, which includes communication vision, social media and website branding plan, initial schedule for the activities, etc. The strategy will be reviewed and revised yearly, if necessary, using statistics and feedback from KPI measurements and dissemination activities for improvement and necessary adjustments.

The main purpose of the document is to introduce the communication and dissemination strategy together with internal communication plan, communication & dissemination tools, promotional materials, dissemination activities, as well as KPIs, to measure the success of the implemented tools and activities. The document is directly connected to the Task 8.2 (PROBONO Liaison Activities) and D8.5 Liaison Activities and Event Participation (I) by pointing out liaison activities with other EU projects and event participation plan. The implementation of the strategy described in this deliverable will be presented and explained in D8.2, D8.3, and D8.4. Periodic Reports.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPS/Deliverables

Chapter 2 of this document will explain the communication vision and internal communication plan for working together with the respective partners. The chapter will provide detailed information about the use of the Communication Committee, which plays a vital role in the successful communication and dissemination strategy. Chapter 3 will describe communication and dissemination objectives and developed strategies that will be used to accomplish them. While Chapter 4 will describe the communication and dissemination strategy, Chapter 5 will present the communication and dissemination tools and how these tools will be used to create awareness and distribute information on the project. Chapter 6 will give brief information about recognition of EU funding and the rules for flag and disclaimer usage. Finally, Chapter 7 will explain the communication and dissemination measuring means related to the dissemination and communication tools described in the previous chapters.

As explained above, T8.1 is a component of WP8 and has mutual interdependence with T8.2 since event participation and alliance-liaison activities are also a part of communication and dissemination strategy. The implementation of the strategy described in this deliverable will be presented and explained in D8.2, D8.3, and D8.4. Periodic Reports.

Additionally, D8.1 will use data on stakeholder mappings & characteristics provided by WP2. Additionally, based on the discussion with respective WP leaders, the following deliverables will be the main focus of the communication and dissemination activities:

WP №	Deliverable
WP1	D1.2; D1.4; D1.6; D1.9;
WP2	D2.2; D2.5; D2.9
WP3	D3.4; D3.6; D3.9; D3.18
WP4	D4.6; D4.9; D4.12; D4.15
WP5	D5.2; D5.8; D5.10
WP6	D6.1; D6.8
WP7	D7.8; D7.11; D7.14; D7.17; D7.20; D7.23
WP8	D8.4; D8.8; D8.11; D8.14
WP9	D9.4; D9.6; D9.10
WP10	D10.5; D10.13

Table 2: Deliverable Lists

2 Communication Vision

Besides the general project vision, PROBONO also has a communication vision and different methodologies and tools mentioned in this document will be used to accomplish this vision. The communication vision will define the direction of the dissemination and communication activities for the rest of the project's lifetime.

The communication vision of the PROBONO project is stated as follows:

- Reaching a vast audience: The main goal of communication and dissemination activities is to reach a broader audience which includes specialists and the general audience. It means that there would be diverse communication and dissemination approaches for each targeted stakeholder group.
- Communicating actionable and understandable impacts and outcomes: While supporting, adding value and extending the reach of the project impacts and outcomes, the developed communication vision aims to analyse information and devise an effective way of communicating it for the target groups beyond simply restating the data and general results of the project. Besides providing certain action items for partners to enhance or execute, the communication plan will focus on long-term values presenting future action while providing specific action items for partners to improve or execute.
- Making sure everyone gets their voice heard and each partner gets profiled. The PROBONO communication vision will have two main focuses in this context: 1. Promote the PROBONO project, updates, and outcomes to ensure engagement even after the end of the project. 2. Promote the partners of the project.

2.1 Internal Communication

This chapter will explain how the WP8 leader and PROBONO partners will work together in the context of communication and dissemination activities. To make it clear, WP8 (SIN) will lead this activity with the partners in support.

PROBONO has set up a Communication Committee that plays a very important role in creating awareness around the project. This Communication Committee will serve as a unit to support the communication and dissemination activities of the project. Each partner has appointed one representative to be part of the Communication Committee. This representative will further

help with appointing dedicated members/experts from their organization, to take part in specific tasks (news, scientific papers, newsletters, editing).

Each committee member has taken a responsibility for collecting information and input from their own organization to be transmitted and shared by the WP8 leader on the digital communication platforms. The Communication Committee will have the following tasks:

- Writing or helping with editing articles for the PROBONO external and internal newsletters.
- Continuously updating the events list, both internationally but also locally, to maintain a clear overview of who is participating in which event. It is also important to provide the eventual communication materials that need to be prepared in advance.
- Continuously updating the Monitoring file to maintain a clear overview of communication and dissemination activities of the partners.
- Sending two pieces of content to the WP8 leader that can be utilized on the website in the news section, newsletters or on social media channels according to the Content Creation Schedule (See Annex I). The Dissemination leader will establish a new Content Creation Schedule for the Communication Committee members each year.
- Giving input on visual materials created for the project.
- Helping with possible movie scripts or videos.

To cover all these, CC meetings will be held monthly, with the WP8 leader and the rest of the representative members from each consortium.

Figure 1: Communication Vision

3 Communication and Dissemination Objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy of the PROBONO project will focus on three main objectives: creating awareness, information distribution, and exploitation of enhancement activities. Each of these objectives will have a different focus at different times in the project's lifetime. These objectives are linked to the mission and vision of the project presented in the previous Chapter 2.

Further, these objectives require the involvement of the Communication Committee to carry out the communication activities that will be described throughout this document. Therefore, there must be a close dialogue between WP8 leader (SIN and the rest of the partners/the Communication Committee).

The communication and dissemination strategy of the PROBONO project will focus on three different areas:

1. For the first year, the project will focus on increasing outreach and awareness of its scope, objectives, and planned activities to attract stakeholders and maintain their interest.
2. The project will showcase the delivered outcomes externally for the second, third and fourth years to keep stakeholders engaged and collect inputs. A significant area of activity for the communication and dissemination strategy in both these and the final year will be in support of the Exploitation Strategy in WP9.
3. For the last year, the project will focus on ensuring the continuity of the project and its replicability after the funding period ends and supporting the efforts completed during the project's lifetime.

3.1 Creating Awareness

Creating awareness and common knowledge is one of the essential objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy for establishing solid connections with the defined target audience. Developing trusted relationships with stakeholders, such as GBN-related communities and indirect beneficiaries, including citizens, communities, industry, etc., and liaising with other EU projects are necessary for disseminating the project's outcomes.

Furthermore, creating identity through different means, such as the project website, social media channels, newsletters, videos, etc., will also support the ambitions of the PROBONO

project. To enhance and strengthen the online presence of the project (website, social media, videos), several workshops, meetings and articles will be issued and disseminated with the help of the Communication Committee.

3.2 Information distribution

During the project activities, the consortium will develop trusted relationships with relevant external stakeholder communities in areas of green building, green neighbourhoods, science, technology, academia, etc. These communities have interlinked focuses, which give an opportunity for creating activities for more wide-impact dissemination. Accordingly, various workshops/events will be organized to enhance collaboration, get feedback, and share the progress of the project/early results.

3.3 Exploitation of Enhancement Activities

This objective focuses on activities that could enhance impact through external collaboration, which will help extend the influence of the PROBONO results and tools to be designed and delivered to the market. All exploitation activities will support the project's goals by creating and presenting an exciting story about and around the PROBONO project. It will also ensure the creation of trusted relationships that will last beyond the project.

Thus, the aim of the exploitation activities is:

- To establish a significant impact on stakeholders and the society
- Create long-term relationships with beneficiaries and stakeholders
- Ensure the results are replicable and exploitable

4 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy will focus on developing communication and dissemination activities to create a consistent and appealing narrative for the PROBONO project. The strategy will also serve as a guide for project participants and consortium members when they are giving speeches, participating in events and/or in other ways that present the project.

Although the deliverable is called Communication and Dissemination Strategy (PROBONO GA, 2022), there are differences between these activities. According to EC (2020), communication helps increase the project's public visibility and results by using accessible language. On the other hand, by using scientific language prioritizing accuracy, dissemination activities ensure that the project's results are available to the scientific community, policymakers and stakeholder groups.

	DISSEMINATION	COMMUNICATION
Objectives	Public disclosure of results	Promotion of the project and its results
Audience	Target groups, such as scientific communities, industry stakeholders, policy-makers, etc.	General public, including EU citizens, civil society and mass media
Language	Scientific language	Non-specialised language
Channels	Peer-review journals, scientific conferences, online repository of results, etc.	TV channels, radio, newspapers, generalist website, newsletters, etc.

Figure 2: Difference between C&D

Therefore, different tools/channels will be used in different ways for communication and dissemination activities. The list below presents various activities and channels classified according to the criteria mentioned above (Figure 2).

	Activities		Channels	
	Communication	Dissemination	Communication	Dissemination
Publications	Non scientific Publications	Scientific publications	Press release e-Newsletter News sites articles Blogs	Articles in scientific magazines and blogs
Events	Events for the general public	Stakeholders events	Open Doors Public talks	Market showcase B2B networking
Online	Online promotion	Online disclosure of results	Generalist website Social media	Online repository of results Social media
Meetings	Two-way exchanges with citizens	Stakeholders engagement	Citizens Blog and Prizes Photo contest Surveys Interviews	Feedback sessions Industrial events Training sessions
Media	Mass media campaign	Presentations in scientific conferences	Newspapers Local TVs Radios	Scientific conferences, workshops and seminars
Materials	Promotional material	Conferences proceedings	Leaflet Brochure Poster	Publication of proceedings

Figure 3: Differences between C&D activities

4.1 Target group

To reach the dissemination and communication objectives, the target audience has been thoroughly defined by WP2 (Social and Behavioural Innovations). Based on the drawn map, the PROBONO Target Stakeholder & Audience groups table (See Table 3) was established. This target group was further developed from the initial DoA, but it kept a close resemblance to what was initially stated in the document. The table will be improved in D8.2 when the final version of the PROBONO Target Stakeholder & Audience groups list is published in D2.1.

Target Audience Activities	Energy providers	Building constructors	Cities, Urban Planners	Government	Public R&D	Industry R&D/ R&I	IT experts from SMEs	Academia
Website/Social Media Channels	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press materials	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Promotional and marketing materials	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletter	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Academic Publications			X		X	X		X
Workshops & Roundtables	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 3: Target Stakeholder & Audience Groups

4.2 Keywords and messages

The communication and dissemination strategy includes the usage of keywords and key messages regarding awareness creation, information distribution, and exploitation enhancement. In creating a story for the PROBONO project, keywords and key messages will be helpful to:

- Help spread the project objective and messages
- Increase awareness of how research and innovation can tackle emerging challenges and positively impact society while highlighting how the H2020 and EU-funded research helped realize these goals.
- Inform and demonstrate societal and economic benefits generated by PROBONO to a wide range of audiences outside the core project target groups.

- Communicate results and success stories while stimulating positive emotions through the demonstration of the social value created the demonstration of social welfare enhancement and social added value generated.

Keywords are descriptive and informational words of the project that have the function of highlighting the project through these specific words and making it more visible. Keywords also help in online settings where search engines will direct the users towards the projects through keywords.

In the PROBONO project keywords will also help better identify the project when disseminated, attract stakeholders, and make it stand out from other projects. The project has been assigned the following fixed EC keywords:

Low/nearly zero &-energy positive buildings, Energy management in buildings, Renovation, Integration of renewables, Automation and control systems.

The project has further been assigned the following additional keywords:

Building Information Model (BIM), Green Buildings and Neighbourhood (GBN), Energy Performance of Buildings, Building Integrated Photovoltaics, Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations.

These keywords will be further developed during the project with the help of the communication committee to reflect the most updated state of the project. The keywords should always be used when communicating about the PROBONO project on the following:

- On social media when creating hashtags for posts
- On brochures [digital and print versions]
- On posters
- On newsletter articles, to be used throughout articles as well as searchable keywords
- On scientific papers both throughout the paper and in the keyword section.

5 Communication and Dissemination Tools

5.1 Website

The PROBONO website is available with the URL www.probonoh2020.eu and will function as a main hub and key tool for all relevant information and news about the project. The website will present the objectives, expected impacts and key outcomes of the project.

Figure 4: Project Website

The website will host:

- Executive Summary of the project
- Presentation of project partners
- Presentation of Pilot sites and Enablers
- Dissemination of results and deliverables
- Links to Social Media pages
- Newsletter subscription

Figure 5: PROBONO Website Structure

One of the main functions of the website is to present content regularly to ensure dissemination of the project progress for the target group. To ensure the constant flow of new content for the website, the Communication Committee will have the task of helping with the creation of specific content related to:

Deliverables – the Communication Committee member of each partner is in charge of presenting the public deliverables for WP8 by including the following information: Abstract, keywords, tweet sample, and a content for the news section.

Abstract	The abstract should be no longer than 100 words
Keywords	Keywords describing what the deliverable is about
Tweet Sample	A tweet sample to be shared on social media (Applicable to only PR-worthy deliverables). Please, keep in mind that Twitter has limit of 280 characters
Content for the news section	Around 300 words to announce the deliverable in the news section

Table 4: Content Creation: Deliverable

Events/Workshops where the project is presented – if any partner participates in any event or relevant workshop, the Communication Committee member of the consortium should provide the following materials besides reporting the event details in the Monitoring file:

Images from the event	Images could range from pictures, taken, a figure from the presentation, or the poster of the event.
Keywords	Keywords describing what the event is about
Tweet Sample	A tweet sample to be shared on social media. Please, keep in mind that Twitter has limit of 280 characters
Content for the news section	Around 300 -400 words to announce the event in the news section

Table 5: Content Creation: Event

Specific updates, milestones, and technical news – the Communication Committee members from the consortium should provide information on specific information surrounding the project related to their deliverables, progress, and updates.

In relation to pilot sites, the Communication Committee members from Living Labs should provide content related to the pilot sites and any updates during the project, so the pilot pages on the website can be updated.

Finally, continued fresh content for the project website will come from social media widgets displayed on the homepage. The widgets will be updated simultaneously with the social media channels, ensuring that updates, stories, and visuals are also displayed on the website.

5.2 Social Media Channels

One of the most efficient ways to reach larger audiences is to use digital marketing tools. Besides the project website, the other important digital marketing tool that will be used during the project's lifetime is social media channels. Social media channels are to be used for both communication and dissemination, as per the H2020 Programme Guidance on social media (See Figure 6). This chapter will touch upon the social media channels, a strategy on their usage and specific roles for each partner.

COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION
Covers the whole project (including results)	Covers project results only
Starts at the outset of the project	Happens only once results are available
Multiple audiences Beyond the project's own community, including the media and general public. Multiplier effect.	Specialist audiences Groups that may use the results in their own work, including peer groups, industry, professional organisations, policymakers
Informing and engaging with society , to show how it can benefit from research	Enabling the take-up and use of results
<i>Legal reference</i> Grant Agreement Article 38.1	<i>Legal reference</i> Grant Agreement Article 29

Figure 6: Social Media Guidance

The channels that have already been set up and utilized are [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), and [Instagram](#). A [YouTube](#) channel and Wikipedia page of the project have also been set up to host the upcoming materials. LinkedIn will be used as the main social media channel to communicate and disseminate events, posters, and updates since the platform is dedicated to professionals and experts in the field who are the project's primary target.

The social media strategy of the project will follow four steps: collect, share, engage and measure. For the collection part, all partners are responsible for collecting information regarding events, updates, milestones, and news that could be shared and disseminated. The collected material will be shared with the WP8 leader, who is responsible for disseminating the information. Everyone will be involved in the engaging process through sharing, liking, and commenting on the content. Ultimately, the WP8 leader will be in charge of measuring the impact of the dissemination on social media channels.

Hashtags will be used in each social media post to make the post searchable and increase outreach and engagement. The hashtags can be keywords related to the material being posted or to the defined keywords of the project.

As mentioned above, all project social media pages have been linked to the website to avoid confusion and improve access to the project's content. Posting 'live' tweets, Facebook posts, etc., that appear in real-time on the website allows for better search engine ranking.

5.3 Newsletter

As stated in the DoA, five newsletters are planned to be released to inform and engage the stakeholders about the project's progress, activities, and outcomes. The newsletter will be accessible by subscription on the PROBONO website, and the email list will be built on the subscribers opting in on the website. The newsletter will be sent using a marketing tool and follow a release timeline established by WP8 and the Communication Committee.

The newsletter will be provided with content, edited, and published with the help of the Communication Committee. The topics to include in the newsletter will be discussed at the monthly Communication Committee meetings. Each member is responsible for coming up with a proposal on a topic, event, update, or milestone relevant to the project and presenting it to the group.

The opt-in for the newsletter and visibility of cancelling the subscription will be complying with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Below is shown an indicative template of the newsletter:

Figure 7: PROBONO – Newsletter

5.4 Scientific Publications

In addition to online articles in the newsletter, the website, and social media channels, PROBONO should use specific publications to reach a larger audience. Publications in scientific journals and conferences relevant to the research and innovation activities will target the scientific communities directly or indirectly in the scope of PROBONO. There will be:

- Scientific publications for scientific conferences and journals that aims at the primary audience.
- Publications for the general public that aims to reach a secondary audience, such as the non-technical stakeholders, in order to deliver the key messages of the project.

The scientific dissemination will reinforce the project's image and brand and will help with cross-project liaisons. As the project has committed to producing several scientific articles per year, a timeline will be established with the help of the Communication Committee to ensure the timely delivery of papers and create a strategy on what topics to pursue in the future.

Reporting and updating the scientific publications will be done using the ANNEX III – Monitoring file by each communication representative of each consortium partner.

5.5 Videos

During the project's lifetime, several videos will be produced to assist the dissemination process. The videos will reflect the overall project message and defined objectives. According to the initial plan, two videos will be produced. The first video is planned to be ready in the project's second year, and the second one will be made in the last year of the project. The purpose of the first video is to introduce the project, its objectives, vision, and mission. On the other hand, the second video will present the project's progress and result. The number of videos can change depending on the project budget.

5.6 Living Labs

The PROBONO project has six living labs (pilots) around Europe. These pilots will also serve as a great networking tool for experience sharing and knowledge exchange. Besides other roles, Living Labs will also support wider dissemination of the project results to increase awareness

and engagement. It will ultimately lead to exploitations and replications of the project's outcomes.

5.7 Press-releases

According to the DoA, it has been agreed to release one press release per year about the project and its progress. A press release template has been created and can be found on the PROBONO internal repository. [One press release](#) on the project has already been published in M1.

Figure 8: PROBONO Press Release

5.8 Poster

The project aims to produce several means of dissemination aligned with the stylebook and overall vision of the project. The posters will be presented at conferences and even aid the project's visibility and information dissemination.

Figure 9: PROBONO Poster

5.9 Flyer

Besides posters and other digital materials, flyers will be designed and distributed at different events among relevant stakeholders and consortium members as printed dissemination material.

Figure 10: PROBONO Flyer

5.10 Templates and Style Book

Based on the graphical layout guideline of the project, several templates (see D8.15) have been created for different purposes; however, mainly to unify the communication message and style and to ease the building of communication materials during the project:

- Deliverable (public/private) template.
- PowerPoint presentation template.
- Minutes of Meeting (MM) template.

The templates are available in the PROBONO internal repository within Template (SIN) folder. Additional templates can be created if necessary.

At the beginning of the project, the WP8 leader created the Style book guideline. This guideline will help develop a unified message across all communication mediums for better

communication and dissemination results. The style book presents the project logo, the defined project colours, the font type, etc. (See D8.15).

6 Recognition of EU funding

There are mandatory EU communication requirements which explain how the EU funding should be recognized and visualized in any communication and dissemination materials and activities.

6.1 The emblem and information

The following statement informing about EU funding has to be displayed on all communication and dissemination materials in a way that is visible to the public.:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101037075. This output reflects only the author's view, and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The emblem can be downloaded in different sizes and formats on the following page: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

When displaying the EU emblem, these rules should be followed:

- The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm.
- The name of the European Union shall always be spelt out in full.
- The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana.
- Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.
- The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not prescribed in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way.
- The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.
- The colour of the font should be reflex blue (the same blue colour as the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

More about the rules regarding the EU emblem display can be found in [“The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes – Guidelines for beneficiaries and other third parties”](#).

6.2 Disclaimer

Besides informing statement, the EU disclaimer must also be included to specify that the material reflects only the author's view and that the European Commission is not responsible for the content:

This document reflects only the author's views, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained there.

7 Communication and Dissemination impact/efficiency

7.1 C&D KPIs

This chapter will explain the ways of measuring the impact and efficiency of dissemination and communication tools. Table 6 below presents the preliminary KPI targets as agreed in the DoA. During the lifetime of the project, additional targets can be added as the project progresses.

Target description		Target Goal
Website	N° of page visits to the website	500
	N° of references to the project on search engines	120
Social Media	N° of contacts/followers on social media	300/200
Press materials	N° of press releases	10
	N° of articles	10
Videos	N° of subscribers on YouTube channel	100
	N° of views on the video	1000
Events	N° of participants in the final project conference	200
	N° of international conferences as speaker	6
	N° of presentations in conferences	10
Promotional and marketing materials	N° of brochure/leaflet	1

Newsletter	N° of subscribers	500
Academic Publications	N° of published academic publications	8
Workshops & Roundtables	N° of workshops as co-organizer	4

Table 6: C&D KPI List

7.2 KPI Reporting

Table 7 shows the preliminary KPI reporting table to be used on following up on the dissemination and communication activities. The table is developed based on Table 6 to follow up on the dissemination efforts. It lists the dissemination and communication activities and breaks them down into specific KPIs in order to have a better overview of each of our measurable targets. The table includes a breakdown of the website analytics, social media performance by channel, the reach and performance of the newsletter, and the cumulated events where the project would be presented. Thus, KPIs will be monitored based on this table and Monitoring file. In case of the KPIs don't achieve the specific goals, three strategies will be followed:

1. Digital Marketing tools: Website/Social Media posts and ads.
2. Sister Projects: Liaison activities with sister projects and the usage of their website/ SM channels.
3. Advisory Board and GBN Innovation Cluster: Alliance with the AB and Clusters.

Dissemination activities	KPI	Status period
Website	N° of page visits to the website	
	N° of references to the project on search engines	
Newsletter	N° of newsletter subscriptions	
	N° of Newsletters sent	
	Open rate	
Events	N° of conferences as speaker	
	N° of conferences with PROBONO presentations	
Publications	N° of press releases published in the local, national or EU level journals	
	N° of academic publications in international conferences and journals	
Instagram community	N° of followers	
	N° of post published	
	N° of posts reached	
Twitter community	N° of followers	
	N° of tweets published	
	Total N° of tweet impressions	
	N° of engagements (retweet, like, link click)	
Facebook community	N° of subscribers	

	N° of post published	
	N° of posts reached	
LinkedIn community	N° of subscribers	
	N° of news published	
YouTube community	N° of views	
	N° of videos published	

Table 7: KPI Reporting

8 Conclusion

This document describes the Communication and Dissemination Strategy of the PROBONO project together with defined tools, rules, and KPIs. For a successful implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy, the effort of all project partners, with a particular focus on the Communication Committee, which has been assigned several support tasks in this process, is required. Besides the plan, the deliverable outlines the tools and activities utilized to reach the proper target audiences and goals of the project. To maximize the impact and awareness creation of the project, these tools and activities will be run at their maximum capacity.

The implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy has already started. Digital marketing tools (project website and social media channels) are being actively used. The next step for these channels is to grow the number of followers in the upcoming months. In January, the first external project newsletter, which summarizes the project's first year, will be published for the PROBONO community. After this publication, planning for the second project newsletter will start. Preparation for the first project video will also be another main focus for the WP8 leader and Communication Committee members in the next months. Thus, the outcomes of this strategy and the collaboration of the WP8 leader with the Communication Committee will be reported in D8.2 in M36.

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex I

Responsible Month	Partner Name	PM for WP8	Content to Provide	Description/Suggestion	Due date	Status
November	ACC	6	Social Media Post		11/1/2022	Published
					11/3/2022	Published
	INLE	2	Social Media Post		11/8/2022	Submitted
					11/10/2022	Submitted
	FRHF	2	Social Media Post		11/15/2022	Not Done
					11/17/2022	Not Done
SERCO	6	Social Media Post		11/22/2022	In Progress	
				11/24/2022	In Progress	
December	MM	1	Social Media Post		11/29/2022	In Progress
					12/1/2022	In Progress
	AU	2	Social Media Post		12/6/2022	Submitted
					12/8/2022	Submitted
	AKKA	2	Social Media Post		12/13/2022	
					12/15/2022	
ITA	2	Social Media Post		12/20/2022		
				12/22/2022		
January	UCD	9	Social Media Post		12/27/2022	
					12/29/2022	
	DLR	3	Social Media Post		1/3/2023	
					1/5/2023	
		Social Media Post		1/10/2023		

Figure 11: Annex I ([Content Creation Schedule](#))

9.2 Annex II

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Author:	SIN – Salima Ismayilzada

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Figure 12: Annex II (Content Creation Guideline)

